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Cognitive space “hospitality” in the Karakalpak, Russian and English languages

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Abstract

Concepts have a pronounced structure due to the fact that they are formed at the level of consciousness, and their content is information about the objects of the world, obtained by a person in the process of cognitive activities. The concept of "hospitality" can be considered universal, universal, but practical material shows that different in languages is the structure of cognitive models representing this concept. Each concept expressed by verbal means has its own own semantic form determined by its values, which is characterized by ethnocultural conditioning, since in it expresses all connotative, modal, emotional, expressive, pragmatic and other assessments. Hence it follows that the analysis of each concept is individual, since individual and its specific history. The concept of "hospitality" is a multifaceted structure. How any unit of the cognitive base of the concept under study has a certain set of associations, structure of cognitive space "hospitality" we propose to consider from the point of view the point of view of its national and cultural marking, which will allow it is better to present the images and associations associated with the concept in English, Russian and Karakalpak languages.

Key words: lexemes, languages, hospitable, concept, phenomenon

Introduction

Representation of knowledge about "hospitality" appears to us in the following associative series: guest, hospitable hosts, feast, refreshments, entertainment of guests, performance of national rituals. We structured these slots as follows: the concept of "guest" is considered separately, signs hospitable host are considered in the frame model, and meeting, refreshment and entertainment are analyzed as stages of development hospitality script. Frame "hospitable person" considered from the point of view of the behavior of the subject in the following frame models:

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- a hospitable person - generous with treats, troublesome;
- a hospitable person - showing excessive care.

The hosting scenario is considered in the next logical sequence of events:

- meet and greet
- treat,
- entertainment.

The concept of "guest" as the main associative slot in the cognitive space "hospitality" is analyzed separately. At the heart of the structure of the cognitive space "hospitality" lies the knowledge and representation of this phenomenon. Dictionary Russian language defines "hospitable - it means welcoming to guests"(Ozhegov). Similarly, it is defined in the Karakalpak and English languages, which emphasizes the similarity in the representation of this concept in the mind native speakers of Russian, Karakalpak and English. Analysis of lexical material in Russian, Karakalpak languages made it possible to single out three groups of lexemes that make up cognitive models:

1. lexemes used to characterize the hospitable human: rus: hospitable, hospitable, generous; kk: konakshyl, meymanshyl, konak; uar, konakzhai - hospitable; English: hospitable welcoming;

2. lexemes describing the meeting, the process of receiving guests: rus: to receive cordially, to entertain guests, to bother, to meet with bread and salt; kk: konak kutu, konak; atkaru, konak etu (to receive guests); English: to give "at home" parties, to entertain guests, to show hospitality, to give welcome; lexemes used to describe rituals associated with rites of meeting, refreshments, farewell, etc., the so-called pragmatic idioms or speech etiquette: Russian: "Bread and salt!", "Good welcome!", "You are welcome!"; kaz: Kosh keldinizder!, Terletiniz!.English: Welcome! The concept of "hospitality" is a typical gestalt. Gestalt as a kind of concept is "fixed by the word a holistic image that combines sensual and rational elements, and also combining the dynamic and static aspects of the displayed object or phenomenon" (Sternin, Bykova 1998: 57).

Among the features of the concept of "hospitality" in the analyzed languages, we singled out "participants", "actors" of this process: the "object" is the one who is received by the guests, and the "subject" is the person who receiving guests, endowed with the features of a hospitable host. IN within the framework of frame analysis, we are interested in the behavior and attributes of the "subject". What is the image of a "hospitable person" in the linguistic consciousness of the English, Karakalpaks and Russians? This is the main question we tried respond by analyzing specific language material. We propose to consider the frame "hospitable person" in the following models:

1. hospitable person - generous with treats, troublesome;
2. hospitable person - showing excessive care.

Frame model "hospitable - generous with treats, troublesome" In the Russian language, the lexeme "hospitable" has been preserved since ancient times, which is closest to the concept of "hospitable". "Hospitality" is derived from the turnover "Bread and salt!", Which in Russia for a long time was a greeting uttered by a guest at the entrance to the hut, where A family was sitting at the table. "hospitable man" in Russian linguistic consciousness - this is an open person, ready to generously set the table and generously treat the guests. Among the most common stereotypes Russians T.G. Grushevitskaya calls gaiety, love for the holidays, Russian hospitality, which foreigners in some cases perceived as a burden (Grushevitskaya 2003:325). In our opinion, a "troublesome" owner is perceived not only by foreigners as a person who is overly hospitable. It's confirmed the following language material:

Tea preparation began; the old woman and her husband became fuss around the table, on which a clean tablecloth was laid. The old people treated me diligently, and since I had not drunk good tea for a long time, completely satisfied their hospitality. But as soon as the tea ran out, as Zyablikov noticed to his wife that it would be time to fuss about dinner (A.Ya. Panaeva "Steppe young lady" p.349). Candidate Konstantin Ivanovich greeted the guests joyfully, fussed about the table. The guests modestly waited until grandmother Agafya set the table, talked to the candidate, remembered how they together ... (V. Shukshin "Cut off" p. 147) The word welcome contains the image of a person who welcomes guests, i.e. hospitable - one that welcomes everyone.

“However, you also need to greet?” the first ok: e and the old woman realized. - Or how? My head is spinning - I can't figure it out. (V. Shukshin "Kalina red" p. 389)

The frame "hospitable person" in the Russian picture of the world is associated with signs of hospitality, as well as actions expressed by predicative combinations of the type: accept well, accept cordially, accept with joy. For example:

- Pyotr Alekseich will receive the guests kindly, will leave the house on crutches and sit next to the prince on the porch (P. Melnikov "Old Years" p. 134).

- The old people met me with such good-natured joy, which could touch anyone who did not know her real source (A.Ya. Panaeva "The Steppe Lady" p.372). The word hospitable can be characterized not only by a person, but also the country, house, city, i.e. nominations that have features. For example: The day before, Sanya sent me several books, and I read how now I remember "Hospitable Arctic". I overcame, although not without difficulty, because I read it at night, now falling asleep, then waking up, and I remember that I never understood why she was hospitable: it seemed to me— not very (V. Kaverin "Two Captains" p. 412).

The frame "hospitable" in English is represented by the whole ^ a number of associative words, namely, the following adjectives: "sociable", "companionable" (sociable), "accommodating", "obliging", "amiable" (amiable), "accessible" (available), "amenable" (pliable), "amicable", "friendly" (friendly), "kind" (kind), "bountiful", "charitable" (merciful), "generous", "liberal" (generous), "convivial" (cheerful, festive), "cordial", "genial" (cordial), "open", "openminded" (open), "courteous" (courteous), "gracious" (gracious, J k condescending), "magnanimous" (generous), "neighbourly" (neighborly), "receptive" (receptive), "responsive" (responsive), "tolerant" (patient), "helpful", "philanthropic" (ready to help). Selected examples from literary works of various periods can serve as confirmation of the above associations and also allow you to add them. The manifestation of English hospitality explicated in the following examples, which describe III the concept of "hospitality" through signs, through the behavior of heroes, situation, relationship.

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and Mr. Brackenbridge, in whose house he was, made a point of being very polite to her. (S.Maugham "Theater" p.94). Mr Breckenbridge:, in whose house he was visiting, was, as usual, polite with guests.

Conclusion

Thus, the frame "hospitable person" is represented by slots, characterizing the signs of a hospitable host. In a Russian painting of the world, a hospitable host is associated with a troublesome, fussy, hospitable, in the Karakalpak mentality the image of a hospitable, generous, respectful host, hospitable to to anyone who came to his house, a person, In the English-speaking picture of the world "hospitable" means friendly, cordial, patient, condescending person. Since the concept of "hospitality" is dynamically developing phenomenon, it seems possible describe the concept of "hospitality" in the scenario (or script) "reception guests" with stages: meeting guests, refreshments, entertainment. In the studied languages, the concept of "hospitality" in the script is expressed to varying degrees.

References:

1. James Henry. The figure in the carpet and other stories. Penguin Books. 1986. 453 p.
2. James Joyce. The dead. pp. 35-77.
3. Joyce James. Dubliners. A portrait of the artist as a young woman. M. Progress Pubhshers.1982. 588 p.
4. Katherine Mansfield. The daughters of the Late Colonel. pp. 105-126.
5. Maugham W.S. A casual affair.
6. Maugham W.S. The moon and sixpence. Progress Publishers. M.
7. Maugham W.S. Theatre. M.: «Высшая школа». 1985. 223 p.
8. Maugham W.S.The painted veil. M.: Междун. отнош. 1981. 248 с.
9. Modern English short stories. M.: Foreign Languages Publishing House.1963. 559 p.
10. Александрова О.В. Проблемы экспрессивного синтаксиса : на материале английского языка : учебное пособие для студентов институтов и факультетов иностранных языков. 2-е изд. М.: URSS. 2009. 211 с.

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11. Алефиренко Н.Ф. Поэтическая энергия слова. Синергетика языка, сознания и культуры. М.: Academia. 2002. 391 с.
12. Арутюнова Н.Д. Теория метафоры: Сборник // Пер. под ред. Н.Д. Арутюновой, М.А. Журиной. М.: Прогресс. 1990. 511с.
13. Арутюнова Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка, событие, факт. М.: Наука. 1988. 338с.
14. Арутюнова Н.Д. Язык и мир человека. М.: Языки русской культуры. 1999. 896 с.
15. Арутюнова Н.Д. Дискурс. Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь. М.: Сов.Энцикл. 1990. сс. 136-137.
16. Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. М.: Советская энциклопедия. 1966. 608 с.

